

HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT IN KOLHAPUR DISTRICT, MAHARASHTRA.**Govardhan S. Ubale*****Dr. R. B. Patil****

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ABSTRACT:

Human is the most powerful impact factor of environment as well as natural resources. Natural resources need of the better qualitative human resource for the proper utilization and better management of natural resources and sustainable development of an area. It is also affected the development of economical condition of the specific region. This paper is based on secondary data collected from census of India (2011), population of Kolhapur district. The study highlighted that, the human resource development is not in uniformly distributed in the Kolhapur District due to the uneven distribution of natural resources and physiographic, social and economic condition of the Kolhapur District. This is shows that, relationship of human resource development in collaboration with natural resources.

INTRODUCTION:

Human resource is one of the best resource for the economic development as well as sustainable development of the region. The word 'Development' also implies of 'growth' and 'change' for the betterment as well as improvement in regional level. There are so many powerful indicators and it is very difficult to take all the indicators of human resource development. It is observed that the planning and management for development is generally done at the macrolevel. The quality of human resource is depends on technological development, social status, cultural character and economic condition. The human resource development is presented with increasing productivity with quality development an achieving aims in a changeable economical as well as social environment. This will be also helpful to get a proper human resource development plan.

STUDY AREA:-

The Kolhapur district is a part of Deccan plateau and western Maharashtra and extremely southern part of Maharashtra state is Kolhapur district lies between 15°43' north to 17° 17' north latitude and 72° 40' east to 74° 42' east longitude. The Kolhapur district comprises 7620 sq. km area which is 2.5 % of the state. The general height of the district is 1000 mtrs and administratively divided into 12 tahsils supports 38, 74,015 population (2011). In general the physiographic arrangement of the district has Sahyadri hills in a north-south direction, plateau area situated to the east of the Sahyadri hills and eastern plain area and Belgaum district of Karnataka state in the south. The climate of Kolhapur is generally temperate. Minimum temperature of the district is 14° c and maximum is 36.9° c. The average

annual rainfall is 2063.67 mm. The decadal growth rate (2001- 2011) of population is 10.99 per cent. From the Kolhapur district around 70% of total population lives in rural area. The middle rivers and tributaries i. e. Warna, Panchganga, Kumbhi, Kasari, Bhogavati, Tulasi, Dhamani, Jambhali, Hiranyakeshi, Dudhganga, Vedhganga and Ghatprabha all these river flows from the west to east towards the Bay of Bengal. In the study area also found variety of utilization of land due to the physical setting and socio economic aspects of the district.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:

The present paper has main objective to find the levels of human resource development and some objectives are follows.

- 1) To highlighted the human resources in terms of quality and quantity in the study region.
- 2) To find out the levels of human resource development in the study region at the tahsil level.
- 3) To suggest the planning strategies for improving the level of human resource development in the study region.

DATABASE AND METHODOLOGY:

The present study is based on the secondary source of data. Secondary data also obtained from census of India (2011), socio-economic abstract of Kolhapur district (2011). The census data has tabulated in form of table.

In this paper ranking co-efficient method is adopted for the analyses of levels of human resource development in the Kolhapur district. For this co-efficient of ranking method we have used the various indicators such as, Population density, work-participation, sex ratio, literacy, urban population, education facility, Post-office and health facilities. Collected data is processed and presented in the table form for representation of co-efficient index.

DISCUSSION:

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Sr. no.	Tahsil	Population Density R1	Work - participation R2	Sex-ratio R3	Literacy R4	Urban Popu. R5	Post Office R6	Edu . Faci . R7	Healt h Faci. R8	Σ R	Co-effi. Index
1	Shuwadi	10	8	2	10	7	11	1	10	59	7.37
2	Panhala	5	6	10	4	8	8	9	9	59	7.37
3	Hatkanangle	2	12	12	2	2	2	1	1	34	4.25

4	Shirol	3	10	9	3	3	1	1	3	33	4.12
5	Karvir	1	11	11	1	1	4	8	12	49	6.12
6	Bavda	12	2	6	12	-	9	1	2	44	5.5
7	Radhanagri	9	1	8	8	-	7	1	5	39	4.87
8	Kagal	6	4	7	5	4	3	1	6	36	4.5
9	Bhudargad	7	3	5	6	-	6	11	7	45	5.62
10	Ajra	8	9	1	9	5	10	12	8	62	7.75
11	Gadhinglaj	4	7	4	7	6	5	10	4	47	5.87
12	chandgad	11	5	3	11	-	12	1	11	54	6.75

(Source- Census of India-2011)

Above table also shows the, human resource development in Kolhapur district with demographic variables such as, population density, sex-ratio, literacy, urban population etc. For the processing and analyses of the data also adopted for all variables to find out ranking on co- efficient index method. Formula of co-efficient index as fallows,

$$\text{Co-efficient Index} = \frac{\sum R}{N}$$

Where,

$\sum R$ = Sum of Ranks

N = No of Variables

The co-efficient index also shows that Kolhapur district has human resource development in medium form. The low co-efficient index is 4.12 in Shirol tahasil shows highly human resource development due to the fertile soil, development of agriculture, development of sugarcane industries and highest index found, which is 7.37 in two tahsils also i.e. Shahuwadi and Panhalatahsil due to the physiographic setting of this region. In these tahsils also occur hilly region which is part of Sahyadri mountain region. So there are human resource development is low. Kolhapur district can be divided in to three categories by the co-efficient index, these categories or region as follows;

- 1) Dynamic region (Co-efficient index below 6)
- 2) Prospective region (Co-efficient index between 6 to 7)
- 3) Problematic region (Co-efficient index above 7)

1) DYNAMIC REGION:

The highest proportion of urban population, agricultural field is very developed, advanced in industrial sector and educational status as well as health status are well in this region, so development of this region is very better than other region. The dynamic region occupies 4171.3sq. km. area

and 18,98,844 population is concentrated in this region included Hatkanangle, Shirol, Gagan Bavda, Radhanagari, Kagal, Bhudargad and Gadhinglajtasil. In this region the concentration of Co-operative sugar industries are very high, due to this reason sugar cane crop (Economic crop) is highly yielding in this region. Shirol, Hatkanangle and Kagaltahsils are highly dynamic and economically developed region. Shirol tahsil gets first rank in the dynamic region of human resource development, due to the agricultural as well as industrial development also. Hatkanangle tahsil gets second rank due to the highly developed agriculture sector. Kagaltahsil gets third rank, because of Kagal MIDC, sugar factories as well as sufficient educational and health facilities.

2) PROSPECTIVE REGION:

In this region there are two tahsils i.e. Karvir and Chandgad tahsils. Prospective region also covers an area of 1673.9 sq. km. and occupied total 10,87,647 population. In this region natural resources, educational facilities status are well, but technical and socio-economic levels of utilization of resources is less developed. Karvir tahsil also shows that in literacy and urban population having in first rank but work participation and health facilities are less due to this reason the human resource development is medium level in this tahsil. The human resource development is medium level in the Chandgad tahsil due to the physiographic condition and concentration of remote area.

3) PROBLEMATIC REGION:

In this region included two tahsils i.e. Ajra, Shahuwadi and Panhala. The lack of natural resources, lack of infrastructure, lack of educational and health facilities and less of economic development are the main problems shown in this region and due to this the human resource development is very less. The problematic region occupies 2000.4 sq. km. area and 5,36,672 population is concentrated. These three tahsils present with hilly region so, agricultural area and its development is low. These three tahsils faced problem of less urbanization as well as industrialization so most of the population of this region migrated to the Kolhapur, Pune and Mumbai city for the job, education and standard of living.

Suggestions:

For better development and utilization management of human resource development in Kolhapur district some suggestions as follows;

- 1) Regional development planning should be set up.
- 2) Introducing the awareness program about natural resources and its sustainable utilization.
- 3) Integrated area program should be provided for the improvement of political, social status with educational and health condition also.

CONCLUSION:

Kolhapur district also shows that, the human resource development is medium level due to the imbalance in distribution of natural resources and its proper utilization. The Shiroltahsil represent with highest human resource development due to the agricultural and sugarcane industries development. Lowest human resource development is found in Ajratahsil due to the physiographic condition. In this region balanced regional development is most needed. Development planning should be taken for the economic, socio-political status, infrastructural facilities as well as educational and health facilities. The Improvement in education level and health facilities are essential for planning on the level of human resource development in the prospective as well as problematic region. Better planning for development and integrated program should be taken, Kolhapur district become as most developed in human resource development. If these problems will overcome and solved, this district can be developed very much.

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